

Spectrophotometric determination of tin(II) using 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran as a complexing agent

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Abstract : Tin(II) forms a 1 : 2 (M : L) yellow complex with 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran in HCl medium which is extracted into dichloromethane and used for spectrophotometric determination of tin. The method obeys Beer's law in the range 0–2.0 $\mu\text{g Sn ml}^{-1}$ with molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of $5.46 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0022 \text{ Sn } \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively at 405 nm. A large number of cations and anions do not interfere with the determination Ti, Zr, V, Nb, Mo, W and Fe can be masked with suitable masking agents. The method is simple, rapid, sensitive and selective; its applicability has been tested by the analysis of various synthetic and technical samples including gun metal. In order to authenticate the method, the complex has been synthesised and characterized by spectral methods (IR, $^1\text{H NMR}$) and TGA studies.

Keywords : Tin(II), spectrophotometry.

Earlier methods for spectrophotometric determination of tin mostly lack sensitivity and selectivity as large number of elements interfere¹. The sensitivity is however higher in few of the ternary complexes where measurements were done in aqueous solutions only thus causing complication due to colored ions. With a view to overcome these difficulties, a chromone derivative 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPB) has been used for complexation and spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of tin(II) after extraction of the yellow colored complex into dichloromethane which offers the advantage of more rapidity, reproducibility, selectivity and sensitivity over most of the existing methods.

Results and discussion

λ_{max} and stability of the complex : Under the optimum experimental conditions of the proposed method, the complex in dichloromethane showed absorption maximum in the range of 400–407 nm, where the reagent blank had minimal absorbance (Fig. 1). The absorbance remained constant for more than 12 h in dichloromethane.

Effect of various organic solvents on the absorbance of tin(II)-HPB complex : Extraction of the yellow complex formed with Sn^{II} and HPB in hydrochloric acid medium into various organic solvents namely dichloromethane, carbon tetrachloride, 1,2-dichloroethane, benzene, toluene, isoamylacetate, ethyl acetate, isobutyl

methyl ketone, chloroform, isoamyl alcohol and *n*-butanol in terms of absorbance decreased in this order. A maximum and stable absorbance was found in dichloromethane, which was preferred as the most suitable extractant for the metal complex. A single equilibration with equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane transfers the Sn^{II} -HPB complex quantitatively to the organic phase.

Effect of concentration of HCl, HPB and equilibration time on the absorbance of the complex : The effect of variables on the absorbance of Sn^{II} -HPB complex was

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Sn^{II} -HPB complex in dichloromethane : Curve A—Complex against reagent blank; Curve B—Reagent blank against pure dichloromethane.

Table 1. Effect of various parameters^a on the extraction of Sn-HPB complex

Absorbance	0.290	0.420	0.460	0.410
HCl concentration (M)	0.01	0.02	0.03–0.28	0.29
Absorbance	0.350	0.400	0.460	0.430
Equilibration time (s)	0.0	4	8	10–360
Absorbance	0.080	0.370	0.430	0.460

Condition (except when the parameter is being varied) : Sn^{II} = 1 µg/ml; volume of the aqueous phase; equilibration time 30 s; HCl concentration = 0.05 M; reagent volume = 0.6 ml; single extraction with 10 ml dichloromethane.

^bReagent = 0.1% HPB in ethanol.

studied by keeping the concentration of tin 8.425×10^{-6} M. The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance in dichloromethane were : 0.03–0.28 M HCl, 0.3–1.3 ml of HPB (0.1% in ethanol) and 10–360 s equilibration time for ≤ 20 µg Sn^{II} per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). The order of addition of the reagent, acid and water should be the same in the proposed procedure in order to obtain the maximum and stable absorbance.

The Sn^{II}-HPB complex obeyed Beer's law in the range 0–0.2 µg Sn^{II} ml⁻¹ and showed deviation from linearity for > 2 µg Sn^{II} ml⁻¹ concentration. Ringbom plot between percentage transmittance and log ppm of tin showed the optimum concentration for determination of the metal ion to be 0.32–1.78 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 405 nm were 5.46×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0022 µg Sn cm⁻², respectively. The composition of the complex in the organic extract determined by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper² was found to be 1 : 2. This was further confirmed by the mole ratio method.

In order to get further insight into the structure of the complex it has been synthesized by the reaction of SnCl₂ and HPB in 1 : 2 molar ratio according to the following equation :

The complex [Sn(C₁₅H₉O₃)₂] is yellow in color, soluble in common organic solvents such as C₆H₆, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, etc. however, insoluble in alcohols, ethers etc. The complex is highly stable to moisture and oxidation. The Sn complex has been found to decompose above ~350 °C.

The IR spectrum of the complex shows a band at ~1610 cm⁻¹ which is assignable to ν(C=O) stretching vibration. This band does not show any significant change as observed in the HPB (1615 cm⁻¹). This indicates the coordination of carbonyl oxygen of HPB to the tin. However, the band observed at ~3500 cm⁻¹ due to ν(O-H) in the HPB³ is absent in the IR spectrum of the complex indicating its deprotonation. The appearance of new band at about 585 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν(Sn-O) stretching in the complex⁴. The IR spectrum of the tin complex suggests monobasic bidentate nature of HPB.

The ¹H NMR of the complex shows the number of peaks in the region δ 8.6 to 7.5 ppm due to different types of phenyl protons as observed in the HPB³.

The thermogravimetric analysis of the complex shows weight loss between 350 °C to about 650 °C due to the decomposition of organic moiety. The end result is the formation of SnO₂⁴ as indicated by TG curve (Fig. 2).

On the basis of the spectrophotometric and the above mentioned results the most probable structure of the Sn-HPB complex is :

Effect of diverse ions : Under optimum conditions of the procedure, the effect of various anions, cations and complexing agents on the extraction of Sn-HPB complex was studied by taking their sodium or potassium salts (mg amounts in parentheses) in 10 ml of the aqueous volume containing 10 µg Sn^{II} and the general procedure applied. The tolerance limit of various ions were : nitrate, sulfate, thiocyanate, thiourea and sulfosalicylic acid (100 each); chloride and bromide (80 each); acetate (70); ascorbic acid and sulfite (60 each); iodide (40); citrate (30); phosphate (15); carbonate (10); dithionite (7); EDTA 'disodium salt' (5); oxalate and tartrate (2 each); fluoride (0.1); glycerol and H₂O₂ (30% w/v) (1 ml each).

Among the cations, Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^{II}, Mg^{II}, Al^{III}, Cd^{II}, Se^{IV} and Ca^{II} (10 each); Ce^{IV} (8); Mn^{II} and As^{III} (7 each); Ag^I and Be^{II} (5 each); Cu^{II} (4); Os^{VIII} (3); U^{VI} (2); Th^{IV} (1); Ta^V (0.5); Re^{VII} (0.3); Bi^{III}, Au^{III} and Pt^{IV} (0.2 each); Ru^{III}, Sb^{III} and Cr^{VI} (0.1 each); Ir^{III} and Pd^{II} (0.05 each) do not interfere. Fe^{III} and V^V (1

Fig. 2. TG and DTG curve of the Sn-HPB complex.

each) were masked with 60 mg ascorbic acid; Zr^{IV} (0.1), Ti^{IV} (0.5) and W^{VI} (0.05) with 10 mg phosphate; Nb^V (0.1) with 2 mg oxalate and Mo^{VI} (0.025) with 7 mg dithionite.

Applications : The proposed method is simple, sensitive and highly selective as large number of elements including platinum metals do not interfere. The proposed method is better than the existing methods particularly in

respect of sensitivity/or selectivity and instantaneous reaction of Sn^{II} with HPB¹. The method takes only a few minutes for a single determination. The wide applicability of the method was tested by the analysis of several synthetic (some of them analogous to tungsten brass, Chinese speculum, aluminium tin bronze and ceco) and gun metal sample with satisfactory results. The relative standard deviation of the method was found to be ± 0.0039 absorbance units with coefficient of variation of 0.39%.

Experimental

A Shimadzu spectrophotometer, model UV-Visible-140-02, with 1 cm matched glass cells was used for the routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies. The IR spectra, ¹H NMR spectra and TGA were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1710 FTIR spectrometer over the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} , Bruker 300 MHz and Perkin-Elmer thermal analysis instruments respectively. The standard stock solution (250 ml) of tin(II) containing 1 mg ml^{-1} of the metal ion was prepared from $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R., Reidel) which was standardized gravimetrically by the SnO_2 method⁵. Lower concentration (10, 50 and 100 μg) were obtained by suitable dilution with deionized water containing 0.5 M HCl. The containers of the stock solution were wrapped with carbon paper and kept in the dark place. Stock solutions of other metal ions were prepared at mg ml^{-1} level by dissolving their commonly available sodium or potassium salts in deionized water or dilute acid. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of other ions of known concentration with Sn^{II} solution (Table 2). A 0.1% solution of reagent 3-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran in ethanol (HPB; m.p. 171–172 °C) was prepared and the reagent synthesized by the literature method³. Dichloromethane (Ranbaxy) was used as such for the extraction of the complex.

Dissolution of alloy samples : Gun metal : Sample of the gun metal (0.2 g) was taken in a beaker, dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 2–4 ml of concentrated nitric acid on heating the solution becomes clear, then cooled and the volume was made up to 100 ml. 10 ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml to get a working solution of low concentration. An aliquot (0.25 ml) of this solution was analyzed by the proposed method.

Procedure : To a sample solution containing up to $\leq 20 \mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}}$ in 0.5 M hydrochloric acid taken in 125 ml separating funnel and 0.6 ml of HPB 0.1% (w/v) in ethanol, were added followed by enough deionized water to raise the aqueous volume to 10 ml and then equilibrated once with 10 ml of dichloromethane for 30 s. The yellow

Table 2. Analysis of tin(II) in different samples

Sl. no.	Composition (mg)	Sn added (μg)	Sn found* (μg)
1.	Cr (0.02), As (2), Re (0.2)	10.0	9.8 ± 0.91
2.	Cd (2), Ag (1), Th (0.1), Ba (1)	15.0	14.9 ± 0.30
3.	Co (2), Be (1), V (0.1) ^a	5.0	5.1 ± 1.46
4.	Zn (5), Au (0.05), Zr (0.02) ^b	14.0	13.9 ± 0.65
5.	Ti (0.1), Ta (0.03), Sr (2), Ir (0.01) ^b	10.0	9.7 ± 0.61
6.	Cu (2.4), Zn (1.36), Al (0.112), Ni (0.03), Mn (0.028), W (0.008) ^{b,c1}	8.0	7.9 ± 0.98
7.	Cu (0.081), Sb (0.0085) ^{c2}	11.0	10.8 ± 0.83
8.	Al (0.00375), Zn (0.003), Cu (0.129) ^{c3}	15.0	15.1 ± 0.30
9.	Pb (0.0832), Fe (0.0078), Cu (0.163) ^{a,c4}	12.0	12.0 ± 0.95
10.	Gun metal	4.9% ^d	$4.6\% \pm 1.02$

*Average of triplicate analyses; mean \pm %RSD ($n = 3$).

^aIn presence of 60 mg ascorbic acid. ^bIn presence of 10 mg phosphate. ^{c1, c2, c3, c4}Correspond to tungsten brass, Chinese speculum, aluminium tin bronze and ceco, respectively. ^dCertified value.

organic layer was passed through Whatman filter paper (No. 41, 9 cm diameter, pretreated with dichloromethane) to remove water droplets, if any. The absorbance of the yellow colored complex was measured at 405 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank and the contents of the tin were computed from a standard calibration curve prepared by analyzing different known quantities of tin.

Modifications of the method for containing Fe^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , Nb^{V} , V^{V} , Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} : each of Fe^{III} and V^{V} were masked with ascorbic acid; Zr^{IV} , Ti^{IV} and W^{VI} with phosphate; Nb^{V} with oxalate and Mo^{VI} with sodium dithionite which were added prior to the addition of reagents in 10 ml of aqueous volume. The respective amount of masking agents used was mentioned in the effect of diverse ions.

Preparation and isolation of the complex Sn-HPB complex :

$\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R., Reidel) (0.113 g, 0.5 mmol) was dissolved in minimum amount of hydrochloric acid and HPB (0.238 g, 1 mmol) was dissolved in alcohols separately. Two solutions were mixed and stir for 4–5 min a yellow solid product separated out. The product was filtered through Buckner funnel washed with water followed by alcohol. The yellow precipitate was then dissolved in warm dichloromethane and filtered and put on a water bath to remove the solvent. The last traces of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure resulting in fine yellow product (yield 96.0%). Analysis of Sn : (Found 19.86; Calcd. 20.07%).

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